

eDNAAqua-Plan M3.2 Workshop - Start

Time (CET)	Topic	Lead
9:30-09:50	Introduction + Miro demo	Emilie & Peter
09:50-10:20	Current landscape - T3.1	T3.1 lead & all participants
10:20-10:30	• Biobreak	
10:30-11:00	Current landscape - T3.2	T3.2 lead & all
11:00-11:45	Current landscape - T3.3	T3.3 lead & all
11:45-12:00	• Biobreak	
12:00-12:30	What can be linked between the maps?	All
12:30-13:30	• Lunch break	
13:30-14:15	Future landscape - T3.1	T3.1 lead & all
14:15-15:00	Future landscape - T3.2	T3.2 lead & all
15:00-15:15	• Biobreak	
15:15-16:00	Future landscape - T3.3	T3.3 lead & all
16:00-17:00	Putting it all together	All

Instructions for the workshop

- Introduction to the workshop and miro:**
 - Have everyone zoom in on these instructions and the participants tab
 - Let each participant add a sticky note in the tab with their name
 - Recommendations to integrate: this is our "recommendations garage". Here, we have added the different recommendations and notes taken from the WP2 and WP4 reports. Throughout the workshop, they will need to be integrated into the different landscapes.
- Current landscape:**
 - We will work through each landscape one by one, starting with T3.1 and moving down from there. Each task has approx. 30 minutes for this exercise.
 - Each task will present their current landscape graph. Next, we will let participants add sticky notes with comments either directly on the graph or in the question panels.
 - Finally, we will take the current landscape and add the missing nodes and links in the editing panel.
- Future landscape:**
 - Here, we will again work task by task. For each task we will start with their draft graphic of the conceptual, future landscape. If no such graph exists we will work on the edited current landscape from the morning session.
 - Then, we let participants add sticky notes to comment on the conceptual mapping and answer the questions asked in the second panel to gather ideas about the ideal landscapes and measures we could take to get there.
 - These ideas and measures will then be ranked according to their importance and feasibility.
 - Finally, these ranked ideas will be added to the conceptual future landscape to come up with our consensus vision for the future.
- Putting it all together:**
 - The final aim is to identify the linkages between the T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 layers
 - Here, we will also go over any recommendations from the "garage" that have not been incorporated yet, as well as suggestions from earlier sessions that need to be addressed
 - Finally, we will brainstorm the risks and opportunities of the current and future landscapes

Recommendations to integrate - to move in the appropriate location

Definitions

Catalogue metadata = metadata that describes datasets held by some dataset catalogue, provided as a separate digital object to the data.

Provenance metadata = the metadata specifically to describe who, what, where, when and how of the activities that led to a sample or a dataset.

Dataset = digital object(s) that are the results of the experiment/activity.

Metadata = metadata contained in datasets that describe the experiment, the environment, the activity.

Systems metadata = occurrence = the existence of an organism (at a place and time)

Reference library = the reference (data) that was used to derive some result (for us, taxon classifications) via a (programmatic) comparison.

Sequence repository =

biobanks:
<https://www.iso.org/standard/72879.htm>
//
<https://www.iso.org/standard/74543.htm>
// ISO 20387

Pick and define all the necessary terms from the landscape drafts, e.g.:
- study metadata
- raw sequence data
- processed sequence data
- standard

Current landscape

Future landscape

T3.1

Current landscape mapping

Editing the current landscape mapping

T3.2

Current landscape mapping

Editing the current landscape mapping

T3.1

Draft conceptual mapping

Future landscape

T3.2

Draft conceptual mapping

Future landscape

